
Research Article

New combinations in Orchidaceae of Australia

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Abstract: One new name and 19 new combinations are proposed here for 20 Australian species of Orchid belonging to 5 genera. These combinations are needed to comply with current taxonomic concepts of the respective genus. One new combination for Orchid species of New Zealand is also proposed.

Keywords: Australia, *Bulbophyllum*, *Caleana*, *Corybas*, Endemic, New Zealand, *Prasophyllum*, *Pterostylis*

Introduction

The recent molecular and phylogenetic studies of the family Orchidaceae have changed the generic concept, delimitation and classification within the family. Based on the current, stable and wider generic circumscriptions in the family Orchidaceae (Janes & Duretto, 2010; Miller & Clements, 2014; Chase et al., 2015), one new name and 19 new combinations are required for 20 Orchid species of Australia, belonging to five genera [*Bulbophyllum* Thouars, *Caleana* R.Br., *Corybas* Salisb., *Prasophyllum* R.Br. and *Pterostylis* R.Br.], which are made here. One new combination for Orchid species of New Zealand is also proposed. We followed the guidelines and recommendations of Article 41 in Turland et al. (2018).

Nomenclature

Bulbophyllum continentale (D.L.Jones, M.A.Clem. & H.C.Zimmer) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Adelopetalum continentale* D.L.Jones, M.A.Clem. & H.C.Zimmer, *Phytotaxa* 678(1): 88. 2024.

Holotype: Australia, Cottan-Bimbang National Park, 9 April 2023, *Bruhl & Quinn 3799* (CANB-959724).

Distribution: Endemic to Commonwealth of Australia.

Bulbophyllum howense (D.L.Jones, M.A.Clem. & H.C.Zimmer) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Adelopetalum howense* D.L.Jones, M.A.Clem. & H.C.Zimmer, *Phytotaxa* 678(1): 90. 2024.

Holotype: Australia, New South Wales, Lord Howe Island, 20 May 2001, *Hutton 830* (NSW-494145).

Distribution: Endemic to New South Wales, Commonwealth of Australia.

Caleana ferricola (A.P.Br. & G.Brockman) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Paracaleana ferricola* A.P.Br. & G.Brockman, *Nuytsia* 30: 287. 2019. *Sullivania ferricola* (A.P.Br. & G.Brockman) D.L.Jones & M.A.Clem., *Lankesteriana* 21(3): 316. 2021.

Holotype: Australia, Western Australia, Canning Mills, 18 November 2017, *G. Brockman GBB3571* (PERTH08961646).

Distribution: Endemic to Western Australia, Commonwealth of Australia.

Corybas arcanus (D.L.Jones) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Corysanthes arcana* D.L.Jones, *Austral. Orchid Rev.* 84(5): 40. 2019.

Holotype: Australia, Victoria, Piccaninnie Ponds, 16 September 2004, *D.L. Jones, K.J. Richards, A. Pritchard & D. Ryan 19105* (CANB-661360).

Distribution: Endemic to Victoria, Commonwealth of Australia.

Corybas heberlei (D.L.Jones) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Corysanthes heberlei* D.L.Jones, *Austral. Orchid Rev.* 84(5): 42. 2019.

Holotype: Australia, Western Australia, Eyre District, Middleton Beach, Albany, 30 August 1986, *D.L. Jones & T.D. Jones 2435* (CANB-679547).

Distribution: Endemic to Western Australia, Commonwealth of Australia.

Corybas intutus (D.L.Jones) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Corysanthes intuta* D.L.Jones, *Austral. Orchid Rev.* 84(5): 43. 2019.

Holotype: Australia, Western Australia, Darling district, Busselton, ex Golf Course area, 2 September 1986, *D.L. Jones & T.D. Jones 2455* (CANB-681137).

Distribution: Endemic to Western Australia, Commonwealth of Australia.

Corybas tectus (D.L.Jones) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Corysanthes tecta* D.L.Jones, Austral. Orchid Rev. 84(5): 41. 2019.

Holotype: Australia, Victoria, Cotters Lake, Wilsons Promontory, 30 September 2004, A. Pritchard & M. Duncan ORG 4538 (CANB-653885).

Distribution: Endemic to Victoria, Commonwealth of Australia.

Prasophyllum canobolense (D.L.Jones) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Paraprasophyllum canobolense* D.L.Jones, Austral. Orchid Rev. 84(6): 36. 2019.

Holotype: Australia, New South Wales, Central Tablelands, Mt. Canobolas, 19 November 1988, C. Bower (CANB).

Distribution: Endemic to New South Wales, Commonwealth of Australia.

Pterostylis anemophila (D.L.Jones) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Hymenochilus anemophilus* D.L.Jones, Lankesteriana 24(1): 2. 2024.

Holotype: Australia, South Australia, Mokota Grassland Reserve, 1 km north of Mt. Cone, 25 August 2000, R.J. Bates 57244 (CANB-621066).

Distribution: Endemic to South Australia, Commonwealth of Australia.

Pterostylis calcicola (D.L.Jones) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Hymenochilus calcicola* D.L.Jones, Lankesteriana 24(1): 4. 2024.

Holotype: Australia, South Australia, Belvedere, private property called Wombat Plains, 9 September 1999, D.L. Jones, M. Garratt & J. Eckert 16800 (CANB-606695).

Distribution: Endemic to South Australia, Commonwealth of Australia.

Pterostylis cymbella (D.L.Jones) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Hymenochilus cymbellus* D.L.Jones, Lankesteriana 24(1): 11. 2024.

Holotype: Australia, South Australia, 1.4 km along track east of Mangalo-Cowell road towards 'Pootitnee' property, 6 September 2000, D.L. Jones & M. Garratt 17348 (CANB-622384).

Distribution: Endemic to South Australia, Commonwealth of Australia.

Pterostylis david-lloyd-jonesii R.Kr.Singh, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Plumatichilos littoralis* D.L.Jones, Austral. Orchid Rev. 80(6): 63. 2015. *Plumatichilos littoralis* D.L.Jones, Austral. Orchid Rev. 80(3): 40. 2015, *nom. inval.* *Pterostylis littoralis* (D.L.Jones) D.L.Jones,

Austral. Orchid Rev. 80(3): 63. 2015, *nom. inval. et illeg., non* (D.L.Jones) R.J. Bates, J. Adelaide Bot. Gard. 22: 102. 2008.

Holotype: Australia, New South Wales, Cape Solander National Park (Kamay Botany Bay National Park), Kurnell, 7 September 1992, A.D. Bishop J219/18-33 (CANB-740554).

Distribution: Endemic to New South Wales, Commonwealth of Australia.

Etymology: The new name is named after David Lloyd Jones, Australian Botanist and Orchidologist.

Notes: The species epithet *littoralis* is preoccupied in the genus *Pterostylis* R.Br. [*Pterostylis littoralis* (D.L.Jones) R.J.Bates, J. Adelaide Bot. Gard. 22: 102. 2008], therefore, a new name is herein proposed.

Jones (2015a) described a new species *Plumatichilos littoralis* in journal Australian Orchid Review volume 80(3) on page 40 and proposed a new combination *Pterostylis littoralis* (D.L.Jones) D.L.Jones (2015b) in the same journal on page 63 for *Plumatichilos littoralis* D.L.Jones under genus *Pterostylis* R.Br. Thus, both names *Plumatichilos littoralis* and *Pterostylis littoralis* are alternative names for one taxon based on the same type, and were not validly published (Article 36.3 of Turland et al., 2018). Later, Jones (2015c) validated the name *Plumatichilos littoralis* by providing full and direct reference to his earlier publication (2015a) and rejected the new combination for *Plumatichilos littoralis* under the genus *Pterostylis* R.Br. as *Pterostylis littoralis*. According to the Article 36.3 and Example 12 (Turland et al., 2018), the name *Plumatichilos littoralis* was validly published by Jones (2015c) in Australian Orchid Review volume 80(6) on page 63.

Pterostylis gracilens (D.L.Jones) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Plumatichilos gracilens* D.L.Jones, Austral. Orchid Rev. 80(6): 55. 2015.

Holotype: Australia, South Australia, Kangaroo Island, 2.3 km along Seal Bay road from South Coast road, 11 August 1993, D.L. Jones 11867 (CBG-9407735).

Distribution: Endemic to South Australia, Commonwealth of Australia.

Pterostylis longipes (D.L.Jones) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Hymenochilus longipes* D.L.Jones, Lankesteriana 24(1): 13. 2024.

Holotype: Australia, Queensland, 'Nabwood', Stanthorpe, Inglewood Road (private property), 18 September 1996, R. Crane 1624 (CBG-9708281).

Distribution: Endemic to Queensland, Commonwealth of Australia.

Pterostylis nemoralis (D.L.Jones) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Hymenochilus nemoralis* D.L.Jones, Lankesteriana 24(1): 19. 2024.

Holotype: Australia, South Australia, Alligator Gorge National Park, Circle Track, 5.9 km from Ranger Station, 5 September 1999, *D.L. Jones & M. Garratt 16701* (CANB-607292).

Distribution: Endemic to South Australia, Commonwealth of Australia.

Pterostylis oresbia (D.L.Jones & L.M.Copel.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Specularantha oresbia* D.L.Jones & L.M.Copel., Austral. Orchid Rev. 82(4): 53. 2017.

Holotype: Australia, New South Wales, Barrington Tops State Forest, adjacent to Sassafras road, 29 January 2006, *W.M. Dowling 448* (CANB).

Distribution: Endemic to New South Wales, Commonwealth of Australia.

Pterostylis pachyla (D.L.Jones) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Hymenochilus pachylus* D.L.Jones, Lankesteriana 24(1): 23. 2024.

Holotype: Australia, New South Wales, Barrington Tops, Pol Blue Creek, 19 January 1985, *D.L. Jones 1766* (CBG-8506250).

Distribution: Endemic to New South Wales, Commonwealth of Australia.

Pterostylis pagophila (D.L.Jones) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Hymenochilus pagophilus* D.L.Jones, Lankesteriana 24(1): 25. 2024.

Holotype: Australia, South Australia, Near camping ground, Wilpena Pound, 31 July 1995, *D.L. Jones & B.E. Jones 14091* (CANB-664129).

Distribution: Endemic to South Australia, Commonwealth of Australia.

Pterostylis pisinna (D.L.Jones) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Hymenochilus pisinnus* D.L.Jones, Lankesteriana 24(1): 27. 2024.

Holotype: Australia, Western Australia, About 12.8 km south of Salmon Gums, 12 September 1971, *A.S. George 11022* (PERTH-7535422).

Distribution: Endemic to Commonwealth of Australia.

Pterostylis recta (D.L.Jones & L.M.Copel.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Specularantha recta* D.L.Jones & L.M.Copel., Austral. Orchid Rev. 82(4): 56. 2017.

Holotype: Australia, New South Wales, Purgatory road, east of Stroud (Myall Lakes National Park), 18 March 2004, *W.M. Dowling 402* (CANB).

Distribution: Endemic to New South Wales, Commonwealth of Australia.

Pterostylis singularis (D.L.Jones & Molloy) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Plumatichilos singularis* D.L.Jones & Molloy, Austral. Orchid Rev. 83(4): 44. 2018.

Holotype: New Zealand, North Island, Waitemata County, Albany, Lonely Track, 13 September 1958, E.D. Hatch (AK-169150).

Distribution: Endemic to New Zealand.

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References

- Chase, M.W., Cameron, K.M., Freudenstein, J.V., Pridgeon, A.M., Salazar, G., Berg, C. and Schuiteman, A. (2015). An updated classification of Orchidaceae. Botanical Journal of the Linnean Society 177(2): 151–174. <https://doi.org/10.1111/boj.12234>
- Janes, J.K. and Duretto, M.F. (2010). A new classification for subtribe Pterostylidinae (Orchidaceae), reaffirming *Pterostylis* in the broad sense. Australian Systematic Botany 23: 260–269. <https://doi.org/10.1071/SB09052>
- Jones, D.L. (2015a). *Plumatichilos littoralis* (Orchidaceae: Pterostylidinae), an endangered new species of Bearded Greenhood from the Kurnell Peninsula, central-eastern New South Wales. Australian Orchid Review 80(3): 39–43.
- Jones, D.L. (2015b). New Combinations in the Pterostylidinae. Australian Orchid Review 80(3): 60.
- Jones, D.L. (2015c). Validation of Six Orchid Names. Australian Orchid Review 80(6): 63.
- Miller, J.T. and Clements, M.A. (2014). Molecular phylogenetic analysis of Drakaeinae: Diurideae (Orchidaceae) based on DNA sequences of the internal transcribed spacer region. Australian Systematic Botany 27: 3–22. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1071/SB13036>
- Turland, N.J., Wiersema, J.H., Barrie, F.R., Greuter, W., Hawksworth, D.L., Herendeen, P.S., Knapp, S., Kusber, W.-H., Li, D.-Z., Marhold, K., May, T.W., McNeill, J., Monro, A.M., Prado, J., Price, M.J. and Smith, G.F. (2018). International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Shenzhen Code). Regnum Vegetabile 159. Koeltz Botanical Books, Glashütten. <https://doi.org/10.12705/Code.2018>